

Recommendations for Trans and Gender Diverse-Affirmative Mental Health and Psychosocial Support during Public Health Emergencies

This policy brief presents recommendations for affirmative psychosocial care during public health emergencies (PHEs) for Trans and Gender Diverse communities. These recommendations include strengthening grassroots community support mechanisms, creating inclusive curricula for health professionals and working with various stakeholders to provide affirmative psychosocial support.

Background of the study

These recommendations come from TransMHPrep, a research project at iHEAR, Sangath [1]. The project team interviewed twenty participants who provided psychosocial care to the transgender and gender-diverse (TGD) community during the COVID-19 Pandemic. Based on these, the team identified best practices for addressing unique challenges of the community. Community members evaluated and refined these recommendations in October 2024 during an in-person consultation in Mumbai.

Challenges during the Pandemic

The COVID-19 Pandemic posed significant challenges for the TGD community [2, 3]. Many lost their livelihoods and faced food and housing crises [4, 5]. They faced threats and harm from their natal families. Lockdowns cut them off from all support, and existing psychosocial care was unaffordable for most in the community [2]. Many also lost access to life saving gender-affirming care (ibid). The Pandemic harmed the community's physical and mental well-being [4, 5]. Community members, Mental Health Professionals and Community Based Organizations were unprepared, and the effects linger to date.

Facilitators of Change

The COVID-19 Pandemic caused significant harm to the TGD community and disrupted health systems that were already trans-exclusionary. Preparing for emergencies like this to include the TGD community requires a long-term, ongoing effort that must begin well before a public health emergency occurs. This preparation includes mutual aid, community organizing, and funding, supported by multisectoral collaborations among CSOs, national and state ministries, and the community itself.

We strongly advocate for systemic change, which is only possible through collaborations at all levels. We encourage Policy Makers, Civil Society Organizations and relevant governing bodies to liaison with Mental Health Professionals, Mental Health Institutions and Community Members to effectively engage with these recommendations.

Note. These recommendations are part of an evolving document specific to Public Health Emergencies and are not intended to replace existing national and regional guidelines.

Target. The following recommendations are made for Mental Health Professionals, Mental Health Institutions, and Psychosocial Support Providers, including community members engaged in peer support provision.

"I was working mostly in a low resource setting... we also had long periods of halt in our services, because we really did not know how things were going to go...At one point during the early times of the Pandemic, [the whole department] got infected with COVID (and) as a woman of trans experience who was transitioning during that time, it was walking down really uncharted waters, because I did not have a single example before me on how to navigate this"

Participant 15, TransMHPrep, Clinical Psychologist, Woman of Trans experience

"The state is the one with the infrastructure to provide something [like the 24/7 helplines]. Something as intensive as a 24/7 helpline is not something CSOs and CBOs can do alone. We saw during COVID that there was a slew of mental health helplines across the country and there was some national level. So, why not liaison with them and make them queer affirmative."

Participant, TransMHPrep Community Consultation Event, TGD Community Member

Recommendations

1: Strengthen Mental Health Service Delivery

These recommendations are made for Mental Health Professionals and Mental Health Institutions providing care during PHEs.

1. Provide **low-cost or pro bono care** with flexible schedules and **referral systems** to ensure mental health services are accessible and tailored to community needs.
2. **Strengthen existing telehealth services** to expand access to mental health services in remote and underserved areas.
3. Incorporate **non-traditional therapeutic methods** and explore alternative mediums of care such as phone and text-based support to enhance engagement and accessibility.
4. Implement **inclusive approaches in tele support**, including gender-neutral language in intake
5. Set up trans-affirmative support in primary and tertiary care centres in the form of **gender-neutral registration, separate wards for inpatient care, and inclusive washrooms**.
6. Conduct **sensitization sessions for staff** in primary and tertiary institutions, disaster relief camps, care homes for elderly people, correctional facilities and isolation/quarantine centers to promote awareness and inclusivity in emergency response.

2: Provide Crisis Management and set up Community-Based Interventions.

These recommendations are made for Mental Health Professionals providing frontline crisis and trauma care. MHP includes Psychiatrists, Clinical and Counselling Psychologists, Social Workers and Psychiatric Nursing Staff.

“A [client] from Hijra community would wear Mangalsutra, and would come [to session] ...I had to sensitize the people who call out the client's names and who would take the appointments. It's a long way from the main gate; there's a passage that they need to come from and then there was my cabin. And because it's a trust, they're, like, seven to eight OPD clients, and then IP, and a lot of people sat in the waiting area. I think that's why I felt that I needed to sensitize [the support staff] for [TGD] community... because they would get impatient and it is a trust, it would get hot, and we would be in PPE kits for IP.”

Participant 9, TransMHPrep, Clinical Psychologist, Cis-Het Woman

“A lot of queer and gender diverse individuals lost access to their social support ...There was a pandemic outside and then there was turmoil inside. So, what we did at that point of time was we established mental health services, because this came up as a very frequent need; people often calling up the helpline and going, 'I have no one to talk to, and feeling scared and feeling alone and feeling desperate' [and] when people have lost their jobs, and people have lost their incomes”.

Participant 10, TransMHPrep, CSO Representative, Community Member

1. Work with CSOs and CBOs to provide **emergency relief, evacuation support, and temporary residence** for community members while following appropriate guidelines for health and safety during PHE.
2. Collaborate with **Community-Based Organizations** to effectively engage and reach out to community members in remote and underserved areas.
3. Train in **trauma-informed crisis intervention methods** for service provision during PHE, including but not limited to tele-crisis support, emergency evacuation and imminent threat.
4. Develop referral systems to ensure **access to legal and specialist support** services addressing the needs of community members such as gender-affirming services, legal counsel, access to specialists like gynaecologists, endocrinologists and primary care physicians.
5. Promote users to **access community-led initiatives** such as support groups and online communities as alternate mechanisms of support.

3: Work with Peer Support Providers

These recommendations are informed by experiences of Peer Support Providers working during the Pandemic and are made to facilitate collaboration with Mental Health Professionals during PHE. While some are tailored to collaborative work during PHE, we recommend MHPs to facilitate these engagements prior to a crisis as well.

1. Provide **formal training in peer support** and set clear expectations for support provision to ensure effective assistance.
2. **Supervise peer support providers** in administering Psychological First Aid to enhance immediate crisis interventions at grassroots level.
3. Establish peer supervision and learning spaces to foster professional growth and to **train in queer and trans affirmative care**.
4. Explore alternative mechanisms of peer support provision such as **text-based support** to effectively engage with community contexts and preferences.
5. Understand the **limitations of peer support** and create referral systems with specialist care providers including but not limited to mental health care.
6. **Center lived experiences** during care provision and work with a systemic, intersectional, and culturally sensitive lens.
7. **Create livelihood opportunities** for Peer Support providers.

4: Strengthen Capacity of Mental Health Institutions providing training and support.

These recommendations are made for institutions providing mental health training and psychosocial support.

1. Include **sustained engagement with legal aid providers** in training and care provision to stay updated on laws and policies related to the TGD Community and provide appropriate referrals during a PHE related to financial, legal and health related support.
2. Create **inclusive training curricula** to include underrepresented cultural identities such as **Hijra, Kinnar, Aravani, Jogta Communities**.
3. **Include and remunerate TGD Community Members as experts** on curriculum design boards and panels.
4. Pursue continued professional development and peer learning to effectively engage with community members with multiple marginalizations, including but not limited to **people with disabilities, Dalit, Bahujan, and Adivasi Communities, elderly TGD people, people engaged in sex work and people with HIV**.

"A lot of [TGD Community Members] would come to peer support with, 'Hey, I'm actually struggling because I can't access my HRT anymore'. Or 'I was in the process of getting a gender dysphoria certificate'... Or 'I don't even know if I should do [top surgery], because there are so many other health complications to think about, and I don't know who to turn to for advice'... Because you're there to be able to kind of give them space to process their emotions, but you know that that can only help to a certain extent and unless material circumstances change, it's very possible that they're still going to be in that kind of distress"

Participant 17, TransMHPrep, Peer Support Provider, Non-Binary

"[In instances of conversion therapy in Inpatient centers during the Pandemic], the family is not ready to give any information [about the community member held against their consent]. And then what can I do? We can go to the police and then [Police] say go to a mental health place like, yeah, the home or the hospital or anything [not to Police Station], so we just have the information about a community member at risk, and we are not able to do anything."

Participant 11, TransMHPrep, Peer Support Provider, CSO Representative, Community Member

5: Ensure sustained efforts to support Providers.

These recommendations are made for Mental Health Institutions employing Mental Health Professionals during PHE.

1. Ensure **regular supervision** and personal and team mental health and well-being support for MHPs.
2. Create frameworks to **identify and respond to the unique crises faced by MHPs from marginalized locations**, accounting for their shared lived experience with the communities they serve.
3. Create referral mechanisms to **distribute caseload**, understanding limitations of care provision.
4. Create **institutional guidelines on emergency protocols during PHEs**, including recruitment of service providers, role division, remuneration policies, and crisis management.
5. Create specific **mental health and psychosocial support mechanisms for frontline workers**.
6. Create mechanisms to facilitate self-care for MHPs by providing **flexible paid leave**.

References

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